

2,4-Disubstituted Thiazoles

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2-Benzoyl-4-substituted phenyl thiazoles have been prepared by condensing substituted ω -bromoacetophenones with substituted thiomandelo-benzamides.

VERY few phenyl thiazolyl ketones have been reported. Erlenmeyer and Uberwasser¹ prepared phenyl-4-thiazolyl ketone. Rajappa and Advani² reported the synthesis of 2-anilino-5-benzoyl thiazole. Ghalsasi and Nargund^{3,4} prepared 2-amino-5-benzoyl- and 2-benzoyl-4-phenyl-thiazoles.

In this communication 2-(substituted) benzoyl-4-(substituted) phenyl thiazoles have been prepared by the following method: ω -Bromoacetophenone and (substituted)- ω -bromoacetophenones were condensed with benzoyl thiomandeloamides. The condensation product was hydrolysed and subsequently oxidised to obtain 2-(substituted) benzoyl-4-(substituted) phenyl thiazoles.

solution for about 10-12 hr. The solution was stoppered and kept overnight. It was then filtered, dried and the product recrystallised from ethanol, m. p. 134° - 5°.

Analysis : Found : C=59.01% ; H=4.00% ; N=4.75% ; $C_{15}H_{12}ClNO_2S$ Requires : C=58.95% ; H=3.96% ; N=4.58%

2. Benzoyl-p-methyl mandelothioamide⁵ :

It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 140° - 1°.
Analysis ; Found : C=67.40% ; H=4.96% ; N=4.98% ; $C_{16}H_{15}NO_2S$ Requires : C=67.36% ; H=5.30% ; N=4.91%

Experimental

A) The following benzoyl-mandelothioamides were prepared according to the method described by Olin and Johnson⁵.

1. Benzoyl-p-chlorothiomandeloamide⁵.

30 g. of p-chlorobenzoyl-mandelo-nitrile were dissolved in 60 ml. of ethanol at room temperature. 3 ml. of triethanol amine were added to it and a current of dry hydrogen sulphide was passed through the

3. Benzoyl-2,4-dichloro-thiomandeloamide :

It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 156° - 7°.
Analysis : Found : C=53.15% ; H=3.35% ; N=4.05% ; $C_{15}H_{11}Cl_2NO_2S$ Requires : C=52.96% ; H=3.26% ; N=4.12%

B) Condensation of thioamides with ω -bromo-acetophenones and their hydrolysis and oxidation was carried out according to the method described by Ghalsasi and Nargund⁴. The compounds synthesised are listed in Table Nos. 1,2 and 3.

TABLE 1—BENZOYL DERIVATIVES OF PHENYL THIAZOYL CARBINOLS

Benzoyl derivatives of	*Properties	Formula	Found %	Analysis	
				Required %	Required %
1. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-chlorophenyl carbinol	Colourless shining needles, m.p. 98-99°C	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClNO ₂ S	C=67.98 H= 4.22	C=68.07 H= 3.95	C=68.07 H= 3.95
2. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Buff coloured crystals m.p. 91-93°C	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S	C=75.01 H= 4.65	C=74.79 H= 4.94	C=74.79 H= 4.94
3. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-chlorophenyl carbinol	Pale yellow needles m.p. 110°C	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ClNO ₃ S	C=66.40 H= 4.20	C=66.13 H= 4.16	C=66.13 H= 4.16
4. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Pale orange coloured crystals, m.p. 120-121°C	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ NO ₃ S	C=72.00 H= 5.45	C=72.28 H= 5.10	C=72.28 H= 5.10
5. 4-p-Tolyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 87-88°C	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S	C=75.23 H= 5.05	C=75.17 H= 5.30	C=75.17 H= 5.30
6. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 101-103°C	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	C=62.70 H= 3.55	C=62.73 H= 3.44	C=62.73 H= 3.44
7. 4-p-Chlorophenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 92-93°C	C ₂₈ H ₁₄ Cl ₃ NO ₂ S	C=58.15 H= 2.72	C=58.19 H= 2.97	C=58.19 H= 2.97
8. 4-p-Tolyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Yellow plates, m.p. 94-95°C	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	C=63.21 H= 4.02	C=63.45 H= 3.75	C=63.45 H= 3.75
9. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Brownish yellow crystals m.p. 110°C	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	C=61.50 H= 3.44	C=61.29 H= 3.64	C=61.29 H= 3.64

* All the compounds listed in this table were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 2—PHENYL THIAZOYL CARBINOLS

	*Properties	Formula	Found %	Analysis	
				Calculated %	Calculated %
1. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-chlorophenyl carbinol	Colourless needles m.p. 83-84°C	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClNOS	C=64.00 H= 3.98	C=63.69 H= 4.01	C=63.69 H= 4.01
2. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 96-97°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NOS	C=72.66 H= 5.64	C=72.50 H= 5.37	C=72.50 H= 5.37
3. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-chlorophenyl carbinol	Yellow crystals m.p. 115-116°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ S	C=61.98 H= 4.14	C=61.54 H= 4.25	C=61.54 H= 4.25
4. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Reddish brown crystals m.p. 84-85°C	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	C=69.39 H= 5.58	C=69.44 H= 5.50	C=69.44 H= 5.50
5. 4-p-Tolyl-2-thiazolyl-p-tolyl carbinol	Yellow crystals m.p. 84-85°C	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NOS	C=73.24 H= 5.44	C=73.20 H= 5.80	C=73.20 H= 5.80
6. 4-Phenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Pale reddish crystals m.p. 128-129°C	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NOS	C=57.45 H= 3.02	C=57.16 H= 3.29	C=57.16 H= 3.29
7. 4-p-Chlorophenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Buff coloured crystals m.p. 109-110°C	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₃ NOS	C=52.01 H= 2.68	C=51.85 H= 2.72	C=51.85 H= 2.72
8. 4-p-Tolyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 90°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ NOS	C=58.50 H= 3.84	C=58.30 H= 3.74	C=58.30 H= 3.74
9. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-thiazolyl-2,4-dichlorophenyl carbinol	Reddish crystals m.p. 142-143°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	C=56.01 H= 3.44	C=55.75 H= 3.58	C=55.75 H= 3.58

* All the compounds listed in this table were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 3—PHENYL THIAZOYL KETONES

	*Properties	Formula	Found %	Analysis	
				Calculated %	Calculated %
1. 2-p-Chlorobenzoyl-4-phenyl thiazole	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 148°C	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClNOS	C=64.40 H= 4.11	C=64.12 H= 3.36	C=64.12 H= 3.36
2. 2-p-Methylbenzoyl-4-phenyl thiazole	Pale yellow needles m.p. 96-97°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NOS	C=73.21 H= 4.49	C=73.11 H= 4.69	C=73.11 H= 4.69
3. 2-p-Chlorobenzoyl-4-p-methoxyphenyl thiazole	Pale yellowish crystals m.p. 112-113°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClNO ₂ S	C=62.00 H= 4.01	C=61.92 H= 3.67	C=61.92 H= 3.67
4. 2-p-Methylbenzoyl-4-p-methoxyphenyl thiazole	Pale brown crystals m.p. 118°C	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₂ S	C=69.61 H= 5.14	C=69.89 H= 4.89	C=69.89 H= 4.89
5. 2-p-Methylbenzoyl-4-p-tolyl thiazole	Orange yellow crystals m.p. 90°C	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NOS	C=73.60 H= 5.54	C=73.70 H= 5.15	C=73.70 H= 5.15
6. 4-Phenyl-2-(2,4-dichloro)benzoyl thiazole	Yellow crystals m.p. 162-163°C	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₂ NOS	C=57.49 H= 2.96	C=57.51 H= 2.71	C=57.51 H= 2.71
7. 4-p-Chlorophenyl-2-(2,4-dichloro)benzoyl thiazole	Pale brown crystals m.p. 110°C	C ₁₆ H ₈ Cl ₃ NOS	C=52.42 H= 2.28	C=52.13 H= 2.19	C=52.13 H= 2.19
8. 4-p-Tolyl-2-(2,4-dichloro)benzoyl thiazole	Yellow crystals m.p. 151°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NOS	C=58.42 H= 3.07	C=58.64 H= 3.18	C=58.64 H= 3.18
9. 4-p-Methoxyphenyl-2-(2,4-dichloro)benzoyl thiazole	Pale yellow crystals m.p. 118°C	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	C=55.82 H= 3.14	C=56.07 H= 3.05	C=56.07 H= 3.05

* All the compounds listed in this table were crystallised from ethanol.

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